

G008.67 B3

Preselfcal

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Postselfcal - Preselfcal

G008.67 B6

Preselfcal

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G010.62 B3

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Postselfcal - Preselfcal

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G012.80 B3

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G327.29 B3

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G328.25 B3

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G328.25 B6

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G333.60 B3

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G333.60 B6

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G337.92 B3

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G337.92 B6

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G338.93 B3

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G338.93 B6

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G351.77 B3

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G353.41 B3

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